

Anatomical Insights In Orthodontic Bone Screw Placement: A Review

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Abstract

In today's scenario, treatment approaches have been changed to treat complex cases. Traditionally, cases which were treated by extraction only or by surgical approach to achieve acceptable incisor position, now these can be done by new advancements of orthodontic bone screws (infra zygomatic crest screw and buccal shelf screw). These screws provide sufficient anchorage for en mass distalization and intrusion. This narrative review article aims to provide anatomical factors needs to be considered for placing these extra alveolar TADs to achieve maximal stability so that they can serve for the purpose they are being used.

Keywords: Anchorage, Bone screws, infrazygomatic crest screw, buccal shelf screws

Introduction

Orthodontics, dedicated to the precise alignment of teeth and the correction of malocclusions, continues to evolve with the introduction of innovative treatment techniques and technologies. Kanomi¹ in 1997 introduced surgical miniscrews for orthodontic anchorage. Proper insertion at a safe site plays a crucial role in achieving primary stability of these mini-screws. Two noteworthy advancements within the realm of extra-alveolar bone screws (EABs) are infrazygomatic screws (IZCs) and Mandibular buccal shelf screws (MBS). These specialized orthodontic implants have garnered attention for their unique applications in addressing complex clinical scenarios and facilitating precise tooth movements. These screws provide absolute anchorage in distalization and intrusion after attaining primary stability within the bone by osseointegration. IZCs are placed in infrazygomatic region of bone and MBSs are placed in buccal shelf area of mandible. These region provide primary stability to the screws due to their superior bone quality. Anatomically, stability of IZCs depends upon angulation at which screw is inserted, bone quality (bone thickness, bone depth, bone density) and maxillary sinus proximity. Stability of MBSs also depends upon angulation with long axis of tooth, bone depth, thickness and proximity to inferior alveolar nerve, clearance from roots

and growth pattern of mandible. These screws offer additional anchorage points for orthodontic forces and can be instrumental in facilitating challenging tooth movements, especially in situations where traditional anchorage methods may be insufficient. The use of these advanced anchorage devices represents a significant step forward in orthodontics, offering practitioners greater precision, control, and treatment flexibility. By reducing the reliance on neighbouring teeth for anchorage and mitigating the need for more invasive procedures, these screws contribute to shorter treatment times and improved patient comfort. However, as with any innovative technique or device, understanding both the potential benefits and challenges is crucial for orthodontists, researchers, and dental professionals. This narrative review aims to provide a comprehensive resource for those looking to gain insights into the anatomic considerations associated with infrazygomatic and buccal shelf screws in orthodontics, ultimately contributing to the continued advancement of this dynamic field.

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Anatomy of Infra zygomatic Crest Area

Infrazygomatic screws are a subset of extra-alveolar bone screws that are inserted above the zygomatic bone, a part of the facial skeleton, to provide anchorage for orthodontic purposes. IZC is a bony ridge within the maxilla extending lateral to the roots of the first and second maxillary molars from the buccal cortical plate. Superiorly, it reaches up to the zygomaticomaxillary suture and floor of maxillary sinus. Thus, it offers the benefit of allowing a two-layered bone fixation and primary stability that is crucial for securing an orthodontic anchorage screw. From a clinical perspective, it manifests as a protuberance following the curve between the alveolar and zygomatic processes of the maxilla.²

Anatomy of Buccal Shelf Area

Mandibular Buccal shelf screw (MBSs), are orthodontic implants placed along the buccal shelf region of the mandible. MBS is bilaterally placed, anterior to the oblique line of the ramus and buccal to the roots of the first and second lower molars. It is covered by the thickest cortical bone in the jaw.²

Discussion

To treat any orthodontic case, it is essential to see the case from every aspect and make all the possible treatment plans. One of the most important modalities of treatment plan is anchorage. Anchorage loss is a reciprocal response that may impede the effectiveness of orthodontic treatment. If the anchorage unit in the force system is embedded within the bone, the reactive forces that consistently arise will theoretically prevent any undesired tooth displacement. This is considered as absolute anchorage which is often necessary in the treatment of cases requiring maximum anchorage.³ Kitachi⁴ stated that implants can be used as absolute anchorage as implants are placed within the bone and do not possess a periodontal ligament. Kanomi⁵ coined the term mini-implant. He used 1.2mm X 6 mm mini bone screws. According to Kuroda et al⁵ one of the main risk factors for screw failure is its close vicinity to the root.

Hence, taking into consideration both surgical and biomechanical perspectives, E-A TADS were introduced by Dr. Eric Liou⁶ in 2004 from Taiwan. He developed a method for IZC screw placement adjacent to buccal surface of the maxillary first molar which has provided a promising solution to surpass the constraints of TADS. To achieve best results from the application of these screws, it is utmost important to analyse anatomical considerations of these orthodontic bone screws for safe insertion at proper angulation and bone depth. The stability of E-A bone screws is influenced by anatomical parameters such as bone qualities (including bone density, bone depth, and cortical bone thickness), soft tissue features (differentiating between mucosa and attached gingiva), and the close proximity to certain anatomical elements (such as roots, nerves, arteries, and sinus/nasal canals).

Anatomical Considerations of Infra Zygomatic Screws

1. Size of Bone Screw

These are at least 2 mm in diameter and 8–14 mm in length, making them comparatively larger than inter radicular implants. Chen et al⁷ found in their research that micro implants with a length of 2mm X 8mm are effective for orthodontic anchorage. In addition, Lin and Robert⁸ have established the same results noting that the ends of 12mm screws could touch the roots of the molars, which could hinder the en-mass distalization of maxillary arch.

2. Site of Insertion and Angulation

To properly evaluate the site of insertion CBCT of the patient needs to be done. Bone thickness is measured at different angles with respect to occlusal plane. Along with this root clearance and sinus proximity are also considered during evaluation of site of placement.

Lin, suggested positioning bone screws in between 1st and 2nd molars, while Liou, proposed the placement of screw more anteriorly at the mesiobuccal aspect, adjacent to the roots of the 1st molar.⁹ He reported that the ideal site for inserting IZCs in an adult infra zygomatic crest is 14–16 mm above the maxillary occlusal plane at an angle of 55° to 70° according to clinical implications.¹⁰ Lima et al¹¹ demonstrated that the ideal location to put an IZC miniscrew is 11 mm above the alveolar crest, between upper first and second molars but Nazir¹² in his studies considered 7 to 9 mm distance as safest from the alveolar crest if miniscrew is placed along the mesial root of the upper second molar at an angle of 55°–75° with respect to occlusal plane of the upper first molar. This is to make sure that the miniscrew is stable and doesn't damage any nearby structures.

3. Bone Quality

The clinical immobility of OBS depend upon primary stability which directly depends on the thickness of the existing cortical bone. According to Fransworth¹³, the typical infra-zygomatic bone width is just 1.44 to 1.58 mm. Mavropoulos et al¹⁴ has stated that appropriate cortical bone thickness required for the stability of the implants is 1-2 mm. Liou et al¹⁰ measured bone depth at different angulations which was 5.2 mm at 40° insertion angle and 8.8 mm at 75° insertion angle but Chen et al¹⁵ took 5.8 mm as the average depth. According to Baumgaertel and Hans,¹⁶ maximum bone depth was found at 11.48 mm if distance is measured apical to cemento-enamel junction (CEJ) of the molar whereas with research Nazir¹² in his latest report stated that it is safe to insert the IZCs at a distance of 7 mm to 9 mm above the alveolar crest as this region consists of appropriate bone thickness of 4.5mm required for the stability of miniscrew. Murugesan et al¹⁷ and Amri et al¹⁸ recommended use of 9 to 11 mm implants if inserted 12 to 17 mm apical to the occlusal plane at 65° to 70° angulation.

4. Maxillary Sinus Penetration

According to Jia and Chen,¹⁹ IZC penetration through the cortical bony plates and a penetration depth restriction of no more than 1 mm in to the maxillary sinus is advised. Chang et al²⁰ stated that bone density at the IZC site is increased with the age that counteracts the loss of bone quantity at the interface, meaning that sinus penetration had no significant effect on the survival rate of IZC. Further research is required because the literature on the negative effects of perforation is debatable.

Anatomical Considerations of Mandibular Buccal Shelf Screws

1. Size of Bone Screw

Most commonly screw dimension for mandibular buccal shelf area used is 2 mm X 12 mm. Michał Sarul et al²¹ suggest that 10 mm long and 1.8–2.0 mm diameter miniscrews are the preferred choice for anchorage in the mandibular buccal shelf, despite causing more frequent inflammation and prolonged pain compared to smaller screws. The mesial side of the second molar is deemed a safe site for MBS orthodontic anchoring screws due to its flatter slope and greater distance from the molar root.

2. Site of Insertion

Due to an increase in bone thickness in the MBS posteriorly, Vargas et al²² and Correa et al²³ confirmed that the buccal region of the second molar distal root is the ideal location for miniscrew installation in the MBS. As the distance from alveolar crest and angulation of BSs insertion, it results in more cortical bone thickness as it moves distally from the first molar to the second molar.

3. Angulation of Placement

Chang et al²⁴ and Sivakumar A et al¹⁷ proposed that BS screw achieve its primary stability when inserted at an angle of 30° lateral to first and second lower molars. Distal to the mandibular second molar was recommended location for buccal shelf implant placement, according to Athira V. M. et al²⁵ The buccal shelf implant positioned at 30° angulation to the tooth's long axis and at a linear distance of 7mm from the alveolar crest revealed the greatest amount of cortical bone, distal to the second molar.

4. Bone Quality

The minimum base value for the buccal extension of the MBS is considered to be 5 mm of buccal bone thickness for safe mini-screw insertion in which 1.7 mm is for root safety distance, screw thickness is 1.6 mm, and the cortical buccal bone safety distance is 1.7 mm. Chang et al²⁴ suggested that interproximal area to be the best site where we can get adequate bone thickness of 3.54mm-4.05mm if placed 5-7mm below alveolar crest. Nucera et al²⁶ proposed that the optimal anatomic characteristics is the mandibular buccal bone is found at a depth of 19.91mm corresponding to the distal root of second molar, with screw insertion buccal to the cemento-enamel junction at distance of 4mm. Patni and potnis²⁷ proposed that in Indian patients, 8 mm from the CEJ is optimal distance with total bone width of (6.40 ± 1.35) mm.

Sreenivasagan and Sivakumar²⁸ observed maximum total bone thickness is found on the distobuccal aspect of 2nd molar at a depth of 8 mm i.e. (6.41 ± 0.29 mm) as well as maximum root clearance of 5.35mm.

5. Proximity To Inferior Alveolar Nerve

Inferior alveolar nerve is situated in the mandible's body is at its most significant the buccal area at the distal root of the second molar. Therefore, the inferior alveolar nerve is most susceptible to iatrogenic damage when bone screws are inserted in close proximity to the mandibular second molar and towards its distobuccal aspect. According to Mathews,²⁹ cortical bone thickness and root clearance both increase with insertion depth provided that there is sufficient soft tissue clearance (roughly 5 mm), screws can be placed in either attached or movable mucosa. According to Changa et al,³⁰ placement in MM or AG did not significantly differ from one another.

Conclusion

The advent of extra alveolar bone screws, it has provided an ease to the clinicians to correct underlying mild skeletal problems with non-surgical treatment modalities. Therefore, based on the data from the literature, it can be concluded that for optimal stability and fracture resistance, high density and high-quality bone is required which is found at infra zygomatic crest area in maxilla and buccal shelf region in mandible.

The specifications for Intra-Zygomatic Crest (IZC) and mandibular buccal shelf Screw (MBS) procedures outline key details for screw design, placement, and considerations for both techniques. IZCs should be 10 mm long by 2 mm diameter stainless steel screw should be placed 2 mm apical to the mucogingival junction at the roots of the zygomatic crest eminence on the buccal aspect of the alveolar mucosa. The insertion angle should range from 55-75 degrees for adequate root clearance. Optimal bone quality with 5mm of bone depth and 2mm of bone width lies interdental between the first and second maxillary molars, with a permissible sinus floor perforation of 1 mm for bicortical engagement. Movable mucosa or attached gingiva doesn't significantly affect screw stability. Conversely, for MBS, a 12mm stainless-steel screw with a diameter of 2.0mm is suggested, placed 4mm buccal and 5mm-8mm below the cemento-enamel junction on the distal aspect of second molar. The screw should be inserted along the long axis of root or angled at 30°, with at least 1.5mm clearance between the screw and the root. Adequate bone thickness and depth are crucial, with caution taken to avoid the inferior alveolar nerve. Similar to IZCs, the stability of MBS isn't significantly impacted by the type of gingiva.

Even though we have explored factors such as screw design, site of placement, insertion angle, bone quality, proximity to adjacent structures in enough depth but there are other determinants also such as insertion technique, patient's oral hygiene, amount of force being applied which needs to be further evaluated to check the stability of orthodontic bone screw.

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